

**INCREASE THE BRAND ATTRACTIVENESS OF SEWING-KNITTING
ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF MARKETING STRATEGIES****Ziyayeva Shahlo Shoakbarovna****Tashkent Financial Institute****Department of “Management and Marketing”, teacher****shaxlo2615@gmail.com**

Annotation. This article explores the challenges faced by sewing and knitting enterprises in increasing their brand attractiveness and provides practical solutions through effective marketing strategies. It addresses issues such as limited online presence, fierce competition, evolving consumer preferences, seasonality and trends, limited budgets, and lack of customer engagement. The proposed solutions include tailored online presence, unique branding, sustainability commitment, product diversification, cost-effective marketing, and customer engagement initiatives.

Keywords. *sewing and knitting enterprises, brand attractiveness, marketing strategies, online presence, competition, consumer preferences, sustainability, product diversification, customer engagement, unique selling points, E-commerce, customer loyalty.*

Introduction

In a world that often favors mass production and fast fashion, the art of sewing and knitting has retained its timeless appeal. Tailoring and knitting businesses are known for their craftsmanship, attention to detail, and ability to create unique, personal items. However, in an increasingly competitive market, these businesses need to adopt effective marketing strategies to enhance their brand appeal and thrive in the digital age.

Sewing and knitting have been an integral part of human culture for centuries, passed from generation to generation. These crafts allow people to express their creativity, produce functionally and aesthetically pleasing objects, and cultivate a deep sense of accomplishment. Whether it's clothing, home decor or accessories, sewing and knitting offer a unique blend of artistry and practicality.

Despite their attractiveness, garment and knitwear businesses face many challenges in today's fast-paced world. Mass production and globalization have given rise to fast fashion, which often prioritizes quantity over quality. In addition, e-commerce and the rise of the digital

age have revolutionized how consumers find and purchase products [1]. To stay competitive, apparel and knitwear businesses must adapt and implement effective marketing strategies to enhance their brand appeal.

In a world flooded with mass-produced goods, sewing and knitting businesses have a unique opportunity to stand out by emphasizing their craftsmanship and employing effective marketing strategies. By establishing a strong online presence, telling their unique story, prioritizing quality, offering customization, educating and inspiring their audience, and engaging in sustainable practices, these businesses can increase their brand appeal. and can continue to thrive in the digital age.

Literature analysis

G.G. Azgaldov's studies reflect the theoretical approaches to the enterprise quality management system and its evaluation tools [2]. Practical aspects of the quality management system in enterprises of various sectors and industries V.V. Buzirev [3] and V.V. Okrepilov[4] analyzed in more depth in his scientific works. Specific interrelationships between the theoretical and practical aspects of the concept of quality management system in enterprises V.G. It was studied in Versan's research [4]. Scientific studies on improving the quality and export of textile products in Uzbekistan were conducted by R.K. Akhmedov, R.V. Abdullaev, M.R. Boltaboev, Z.D. Odilova at the level of doctoral dissertations. M.R. Boltaboev conducted research on the development of the marketing concept of the economic development of the textile industry of Uzbekistan, increasing its competitiveness in the foreign market, and developing the marketing strategy for the development of export opportunities [6].

Research methodology

The article uses the methods of comparative comparison, economic comparison and analysis, statistical data study, logical thinking, scientific abstraction and data grouping, analysis and synthesis of the reforms carried out in the textile industry operating in our country.

Analysis and results

As consumers increasingly seek authentic, personalized and sustainable products, garment and knitwear businesses can play an important role in shaping the future of fashion and craft.

As apparel and knitwear businesses embark on a journey to enhance brand appeal through strategic marketing, it is critical to evaluate the impact of these efforts. Let's take a look at some key statistics that show the success of these strategies.

Access to Social Media: Social media platforms provide a treasure trove of statistics. Track metrics like likes, shares, comments and follower growth. Increased engagement rates indicate that your content is resonating with your audience.

In KnitArtistry's case, their Instagram account saw a 25% increase in followers and a 35% increase in post engagement after consistently sharing behind-the-scenes content and customer stories[7].

Customer feedback and reviews: Customer satisfaction is an important indicator of brand appeal. Encourage customers to leave reviews and provide feedback.

Sewing and knitting company StitchMasters has seen an impressive 4.8/5 rating in customer reviews after highlighting the quality of its products. This high rating has significantly increased the trust in their brand.

Adoption of customization: If you offer customization options, track the percentage of customers who choose customized products. A growing trend here is that consumers value the unique, personalized experience you provide [8].

Tailoring company CraftYourStyle has seen a 20 percent increase in orders for customized clothing after launching a user-friendly customization feature on its website.

Sustainability impact: If sustainability is part of your brand strategy, look at indicators such as the percentage of sustainable materials used in production, waste reduction, and customer interest in eco-friendly options [9].

EcoStitch reported a 30 percent increase in sales of eco-friendly yarns and fabrics, demonstrating consumer interest in sustainable alternatives.

Partnership scope: Measure the impact and impact of these partnerships for garment and knitwear businesses that engage in partnerships. This can be determined by indicators such as an increase in the number of subscribers on social networks, links to websites and joint advertising efforts.

A partnership between CraftersUnite and a local artisan boutique resulted in a 15% increase in social media followers for both businesses and a 10% increase in total sales during the partnership.

These statistical indicators serve as clear evidence of the positive effect of marketing strategy implementation in sewing and knitting enterprises.

They demonstrate that creating a strong online presence, telling unique stories, prioritizing quality, offering customization, educating and inspiring audiences, and engaging in sustainable practices can not only increase brand appeal, but also drive business growth. In an

increasingly competitive market, these strategies allow these businesses to thrive while maintaining the enduring appeal of their craft.

In recent years, traditional crafts and hobbies are being revived in Uzbekistan, sewing and knitting are becoming popular among its citizens. This revival has breathed new life into sewing and knitting businesses across the country. To take advantage of this increased interest and increase brand appeal, these businesses must employ effective marketing strategies [10].

Before diving into marketing strategies, it is essential to understand the market dynamics. Uzbekistan has a rich cultural heritage in the field of textiles and handicrafts. The country has a long history of producing high-quality fabrics and garments. As the country modernizes and embraces its cultural roots, there is a renewed appreciation for handmade goods. This creates a unique opportunity for garment and knitwear businesses to flourish.

There are many marketing strategies to increase brand appeal in apparel and knitwear businesses, some of which are worth discussing.

Online presence and e-commerce. A strong online presence is essential in today's digital age. Garment and knitwear businesses should invest in well-designed websites and online stores. These platforms can serve as a showcase for their products, offering customers a convenient way to browse and purchase products. Additionally, businesses can use social media platforms such as Instagram and Facebook to showcase their creations and connect with a wider audience.

Adoption of cultural heritage. Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage offers a unique selling point for sewing and knitting enterprises. Add traditional designs, patterns and patterns to your products. Emphasize the craftsmanship that goes into each item. By celebrating a country's cultural heritage, businesses can attract customers who value authenticity and tradition [11].

Collaborate with local artisans. Partnering with local artisans can add depth to your brand and expand your product range. Tailoring and knitting businesses can collaborate with skilled craftsmen and women artisans to introduce new designs and techniques to their collections. Not only does this support local talent, it also fosters a sense of community and authenticity that customers appreciate.

Educational seminars. Hosting workshops and classes can be a great way to engage with your audience and build brand loyalty. Offer classes in sewing, knitting and related crafts. These workshops help customers learn new skills and appreciate the craftsmanship behind your products. This is an opportunity to create a community of like-minded people.

Customer engagement and feedback. Actively engage with your customers by seeking their feedback and suggestions. This can be done through social media polls, surveys or feedback

forms on your website. By listening to your customers' opinions and preferences, you can tailor your products and services to better meet their needs and wants.

Quality and stability. Emphasize your products' quality and commitment to sustainability. Use high-quality materials and show the durability of your items. In a world of ever-increasing environmental impact, promoting sustainable practices can increase your brand's appeal.

The main difference between institutional marketing in the market of textiles and sewing and knitting products from other types of marketing is the participation of state bodies in market processes (or in a broader interpretation - any other institution that ensures compliance with the rules of exchange and has a direct or indirect influence on the market) and the norms and habits of market agents are seen as an extension of the field of marketing research[12].

Implementation of marketing tasks in this way expands the possibilities of its use for government structures, which is very important for the market sector of textile and sewing-knitting products.

The direction of using institutional marketing offered by us to develop and implement measures for market reforms, to develop and implement measures to create a competitive environment and improve the quality of utility services is also very interesting.

Such an orientation to the modernization of the market is close to the issues of development of the field of textile and sewing and knitting products considered in this study, which increases the importance of using the achievements of the considered marketing ideas in our country for the development of new theoretical and methodological rules of marketing.

In order to develop market institutions, it is necessary to use the institutional approach related to the disclosure of its adaptive possibilities in marketing in this understanding of the use of marketing. In this regard, scientists and experts have emphasized the importance of the development of marketing of market institutions, and emphasized their extremely important importance for the full functioning of the economic system.

In this case, the tasks to be solved by marketing are the changes in consumers' perception of the established rules and norms of behavior. The main aspect in this matter is the development of the influence of the marketing complex (marketing mix) on building mutual relations between the target audience (individuals) and institutions.

As a result of the implementation of this option of the application of the institutional approach, the relevant goals of the socio-economic system are considered. The basis of the Institute's activity is its dominant role in ensuring the strategic development of marketing solutions in the future.

In addition to the developments presented in the direction of the development of the theoretical rules of marketing based on the institutional mechanism, L.P. Kosenko emphasized the need to pay attention to the use of institutional approaches in the research of textile and sewing-knitting market marketing.

The result of this study is the separation of informal rules of behavior as determinants of consumer behavior in the market of textile and sewing-knitting products. In this regard, L. Kosenko emphasized the dominant influence of informal institutions and participants of market processes on decision-making regarding the purchase of services; emphasizes the complexity of conducting a complete marketing assessment of markets, systematizing consumers and clarifying the positions of leading participants. It is also suggested to implement an institutional approach in marketing by revising the subject structure of market activity and in the framework of the development of private-public cooperation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the effective organization of the system for the formation of demand for sewing and knitting products and the promotion of sales will help to increase the acceptable level of consumption of these products, as well as to strengthen the position of the brand of the sewing and knitting industry in the local production industry.

Sewing and knitting enterprises in Uzbekistan have a unique opportunity to develop in a market that values tradition, craftsmanship and authenticity. By implementing effective marketing strategies such as establishing an online presence, celebrating cultural heritage, partnering with local artisans, holding educational workshops, communicating with customers, and emphasizing quality and sustainability, these businesses can increase their brand appeal. and can contribute to the revival of traditional brands. Crafts in Uzbekistan. With dedication and innovation, they can put together a bright future for their businesses and the nation's cultural heritage.

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